

**AN ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SOURCES
UTILISED TO MOBILISE REVENUE IN ZIMBABWE'S
LOCAL AUTHORITIES: A CASE OF HARARE CITY
COUNCIL (2009-2013)**

BY

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study was to unravel the effectiveness of sources of revenue utilised by Zimbabwe's local authorities since the introduction of the multicurrency system in 2009 in a bid to understand the relationship between sound fiscal capacity and the quality of service delivery provided by local authorities. A case study of Harare City Council was chosen since it is one of the largest urban councils in Zimbabwe and also it is considered the heart of Zimbabwe's local authorities. The triangulation approach was used in the collection of data for this study this means the study used documentary search, interviews and questionnaires. This study attempted to answer salient questions underpinning the main thrust of this study. Questions such as: what are the sources utilised in mobilising revenue by Harare City Council?, what are the various obstacles that are faced by Harare City Council in generating revenue?, Are the sources utilised by the City Council effective in strengthening its fiscal capacity? And lastly what is the relationship between effective revenue mobilisation sources and the quality of service delivery? Of the sources highlighted in this study, Harare City Council has four main sources of revenue which contribute more revenue than other sources and these are: property tax, water sales, and refuse collection and sewerage maintenance charges. This study also examined in detail factors perceived as an obstacle in revenue mobilisation by Harare City Council during the period of 2009-2013, and some of these factors include: limited access to foreign currency by ratepayers, complicated and non-transparent local revenue collection system, central government intervention and corruption. In terms of local authorities' fiscal capacity, this study found out that though sustainable sources of revenue can strengthen the fiscal capacity of local authorities, factors such as minimum level of central government intervention and promotion of good governance principles are also equally important in strengthening the fiscal capacity of local authorities. In relation to service delivery, it was proven that a strong revenue base is important in determining the quality of service delivery since the two aspects are inseparable. Some recommendations were proffered so as to maximise the fiscal capacity of local authorities and in particular Harare City Council. These recommendations include: minimal levels of central government intervention, amendment of the Urban Councils Act [25:19] to be in line with the new constitution, improving the system of administration and encouragement of full citizen participation in the decision making process of local authorities.

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Acronyms

AFDB	African Development Bank
CBD	Central Business District
CHRA	Combined Harare Residents Association
EXIM Bank China	Export Import Bank of China
GNU	Government of National Unity
HCC	Harare City Council
HRT	Harare Residents Trust
MPOI	Mass Public Opinion Institute
RDCA	Rural District Council Act [25:13]
UCA	Urban Councils Act [25:15]
UCAZ	Urban Councils Association of Zimbabwe
US\$	United States Dollar
UNDP	United Nations Development Program
ZI	Zimbabwe Institute
ZIMSTAT	Zimbabwe National Statistical Agency
ZINARA	Zimbabwe National Roads Administration

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

The current structure of local authorities in Zimbabwe is a result of the centre-local relationships defined by both the Urban Councils Act (UCA) [29:15] and the Rural District Councils Act (RDCA) [29:13]. Thus decentralisation of functions and authorities in order to enhance better administration of urban and rural areas since it brings the government close to the people in the local area. One way of decentralising from centre to local is through generation and management of local revenue which is fiscal decentralisation. This relieves the financial burden from the central government and allowing the local authorities to administer the local areas in a way that they deem possible and desirable. This chapter seeks to capture the main aspects of the research project that is the background of the problem, statement of the problem, justification of the study, methodology limitations and delimitations of the study.

1.1 Background of the Problem

Many developing countries, especially since the 1990's, have embarked on programmes of democratic decentralisation that are aimed at creating local self-governing systems that are democratic, relatively autonomous and effective in delivering services (Olowu 2002:1). A sound revenue system for local governments is an essential pre-condition for the success of fiscal decentralisation (Olowu and Wunsch 2003: 12). Fiscal decentralisation refers to the shifting of financial power to the local level. It involves increasing or reducing conditions on the inter-government transfer of resources and giving local jurisdictions greater authority to generate their own revenue and the autonomy to make their own plans (Oates 2001:45). Chirisa and Jonga (2009:168) highlight that fiscal decentralisation is imperative for the effective and efficient financial management of urban councils.

It is therefore the main purpose of this study is to examine the extent to which Zimbabwe's local authorities have been fiscally decentralised, focusing on the effectiveness of the revenue mobilisation sources. Some of the sources used by the Harare City Council in mobilising revenue include rates on property and land, revenue from service delivery, user fees, fines and penalties, licence fees, central government allocation to the local authorities , revenue generating project lease of land and rentals on property among others. This study is using the Harare City Council as a case study from 2009 – 2013 the period of the Government of National Unity in Zimbabwe also a period where economy of the nation had begun to stabilise due to the multicurrency regime system which was adopted in 2009.

According to Economics Help, Zimbabwe's macro-economic environment by December 2008 was very unstable, characterised by hyperinflation reaching a monthly rate of 79.6 billion%, shortages of basic commodities, foreign currency and even the Zimbabwean dollar. According to Bland (2010) http://www.rti.org/pubs/zimbabwe_local_governance_g_bland_pad.pdf the negative effects of the macro-economic collapse is that the local authorities were left broke, such that the economy was slowly rising from rock bottom by 2009 as US\$ became available and some measure of stability appeared in the economy. The economic and political environment began stabilising in 2009 when the Government of National Unity (GNU) was institutionalised. The new government adopted a multi-currency system where the United States Dollar (US\$), the South African Rand (ZAR), Great Britain Pound (GBP), Botswana Pula (P) and the Euro became major currencies in the market. While these five foreign currencies were granted official status, the United States dollar has become the principal currency. Evidenced by the national budget estimates denominated in US dollars, a strong preference for the US dollar for non-cash transaction in the market and even the payment systems (Kramarenko 2010:3).

The pre-GNU period saw the macro-economic environment greatly affecting the revenue mobilisation methods of the Harare City Council for example, City residents were failing to own up to their obligation of paying up their rates in full and on time. This resulted in ineffective financial management systems, which in turn led to the charging of low or non-existent tariffs, failure to recover losses from important services such as water and sewer provision and poor accounting systems (Coutinho 2010:71) which then resulted in weak financial capacity of local authorities. However, the new economic and political dispensation brought with it its own challenges for local authorities such as rate payers failing to pay the council charges due to liquidity challenges which made councils to be inefficient in collecting monies which they would have billed their customers.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The focus of this study is on the effectiveness of sources utilised in mobilising revenue by the Harare City Council from the period of 2009 – 2013, the period of the Government of National Unity (GNU). Prior to the GNU period, the City Council had a plethora of challenges in mobilising its own revenue base due to the economic meltdown experienced from 2000-2008. Some of the challenges faced by the Harare City Council include: revenue leakages particularly property tax avoidance, evasion and exemptions. For example Coutinho (2010:73) argues that exemption or delay in payment of bills by government and at times failure to pay up results in

local councils losing between 5%-7% of revenue. Most of this exemption is done on high valued properties utilised by the central government. The gravity of this problem of property tax evasion, avoidance and exemption is supported by the example given by Coutinho (2010:78) further argues that property rates which used to generate more revenue in the early 2000s at an average of 30% of the total budget, was now generating revenue at 20.8% of the total budget by 2010. Poor capacity to collect taxes due to the use of ineffective financial management systems and according to (Coutinho 2010:71) this problem can be attributed to the failure of ensuring effective financial management systems that result in levying of sub-economic tariffs and poor financial accounting systems.

Another problem that has been affecting revenue mobilisation by the City of Harare is the Urban Councils Act [29:15] of 1996, particularly section 219(1) (c), which stipulates that before any new tariffs are imposed, the Council must seek approval from the Minister of Local Government. Thus the Act has become an impediment in the smooth administration of revenue mobilisation by the City of Harare. In addition to the above challenges, the Harare City Council in partnership with a South African entity called EasyPark, made a partnership agreement in which they levy motorists who wish to park their vehicles in the Central Business District (CBD). Though effective, the system used has loopholes in the sense that the officers who collect the levied fee, at times deliberately forget to write an invoice and put the money in their pockets and also the period of after hours, no money can be collected since all officers will have signed out for duty. The effect of these two challenges is that less revenue will be accounted for against the actual amount that could have been generated.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

This research intends to examine:

- The revenue mobilisation sources utilised by the Harare City Council
- The effectiveness of the revenue mobilisation sources towards enhancing service delivery
- Factors that can possibly affect the collection of revenue by Harare City Council.
- The possible action that can be taken to improve mobilisation of revenue by the City of Harare.

1.4 Research Questions

This study seeks to answer questions like:

- What are the revenue mobilisation sources utilised by the Harare city council?

- What other factors can be considered to be an obstacle in revenue mobilisation by the Harare City Council?
- How effective are these revenue mobilisation sources towards enhancing service delivery?
- What is the relationship between sound revenue base and enhance service delivery?

1.5 Hypothesis

Sustainable sources of revenue strengthen the fiscal capacity of local authorities.

1.6 Justification of the Study

The success of fiscal decentralisation depends on a sound revenue system for local governments (Olowu and Wunsch 2003:12). Hence this study seeks to contribute in understanding and possibly solving the problem of ineffective revenue mobilisation by the Harare City Council. Having noted some of the problems faced by the City of Harare in collecting its own revenue, it becomes imperative to try and find the possible solution to property rates evasion and avoidance and ways of enhancing revenue mobilisation by local authorities. Furthermore, the fact that there is little research that has been covered so far about revenue mobilisation and self- financing of local authorities, this study is justified in seeking to contribute to the body of knowledge currently available within the area of revenue mobilisation by local authorities in general and particularly in Zimbabwe. For example Zhou and Chilunjika (2013) wrote an article about challenges of self-financing in local authorities: the case of Zimbabwe, also Coutinho (2010) wrote about sources of local government financing and Olowu (2002) who wrote about property taxation and democratic decentralisation in developing countries. This research also seeks to examine if ineffective revenue mobilisation instruments can be linked to poor financial capacity of local authorities which in turn will affect the kind of service delivery by City of Harare. Thus ineffective revenue mobilisation is associated with issues such as property tax or rate avoidance and evasion, weak revenue collection systems and excessive intervention by central government particularly the unlimited powers of the Minister of Local Government, who has unfettered powers to approve or disapprove any council increments by the local council.

This study is going be helpful to the city fathers, local and national policy makers and the strategic planners of the city for them to realise possible ways of strengthening mobilisation of revenue for local authorities and breakaway from the problem of only relying on allocations from the central government as this will make local authorities to become subservient to the central government The inquiry is also going to be of benefit to the interested stakeholders like

the Combined Harare residents association (CHRA), Harare Residents Trust (HRT) and players in the market who wish to partner with the Harare city council.

1.7 Methodology

This study will use methods and instruments to collect data which included interviews, questionnaires and documentary review. According to Coolican (2009), a survey consists of asking a relatively large number of people for information. It encompasses measurement procedures that involve asking questions to respondents (interviews) or obtaining information by pencil and paper methods for example by means of questionnaires.

1.7.1 Questionnaires

Payne and Payne (2004:186) note that questionnaires are a set of questions which can be answered by targeted respondents of the research through various means that is either face-face interviews or a self-completion of structured or unstructured questions on paper. In this study, questionnaires will be used as one of the instruments to collect data key respondents included the management personnel from the Harare City Council (HCC), department of revenue collection, the management of the Urban Councils Association of Zimbabwe, Harare Residents Trust (HRT), Combined Harare Residents Association (CHRA) and the chairperson or clerk of the Parliamentary Portfolio Committee on Local Government, Rural and Urban Development. This is a balanced proportion as these targeted respondents have vast knowledge concerning governance of local authorities and its management. One of the strengths of using this instrument of data collection is that there is uniformity of questions which makes the collected data easy to compare and analyse compared to an interview. However one of the disadvantages include, an issue of time where it can take long for some respondents to fill the questionnaire

1.7.2 Interviews.

Polit and Hungler (1991), define an interview as a means of gathering data by interaction between an interviewer and the interviewee. This study will use this instrument in collecting data and the targeted respondents will include the chairperson or clerk of the Parliamentary Portfolio Committee of Local Government and the Revenue collection Manager of the Harare City Council.

Just like other instruments and methods, the strength with interviews lies in the fact that an interviewee can respond in a way that is comfortable to him and the interviewer can ask more questions of clarification in the case that the response is not clear to him. Disadvantages of this instrument include digression from the main question of the research as the both the

interviewee and interviewer may end up discussing questions which are not at the core of the research of which in the end this may lead to the collection of inappropriate data for the research.

1.7.3 Documentary Search

Payne and Payne (2004:60) note that documentary search has to do with investigation, interpretation and identification of the most prominent documents whether public or private. This research will use journal articles, information from the internet, and books with information related to revenue mobilisation. This method is crucial particularly considering that it can gather data rich in content both in primary and secondary form. Primary data is the information which has not yet been published but collected by various legit independent research organisations such as Mass Public Opinion (MPOI), Zimbabwe Institute (ZI) and AFROBAROMETER; Hansard booklets from the parliament and reports from various institutions like Harare Residents Trust (HRT), Combined Harare Residents Association (CHRA) and Urban Councils Association of Zimbabwe (UCAZ). These had some information on local governance management in respect to revenue mobilisation techniques which the Harare City Council employs.

1.7.4 Data Presentation and Analysis

In analysing the data this study used tables, graphs and pie charts. These tables and figures are much easier to use as methods of data presentation and also they are easy to understand and interpret. Complementing these methods of data presentation is data analysis where an explanation and analysis is given concerning the data presented.

1.8 Delimitations

The area of study entails an inquiry on the council of the city of Harare and hence it is confined to Harare City Council one of the 30 urban councils governed by the Urban Councils Act Chakaipa 2010:36 in De Visser (2010). Also the respondents involved in this study include the Harare City Council management personnel from the Department of revenue collection, advocacy groups like the Combined Harare Residents Association (CHRA), Harare Residents Trust (HRT) and Urban Councils Association of Zimbabwe (UCAZ) who have a strong background and understanding in the discourse of revenue collection. The areas in which the city council has influence and relations over shall be considered as well and these areas include the locations and suburbs within the city of Harare.

1.9 Limitations

Due to the nature of the study or field, this research is likely to face possible constraints such as access to primary data from the council offices since the area is politically and financially sensitive. Apart from the above, the research is likely to be affected when target respondents fail to co-operate particularly the council administrators and officers within the target departments. Data collected may be unreliable as well considering the political nature and friction between the Ministry of Local Government, Rural and Urban Development and the Harare City Council. The available website of the Ministry of local Government, Rural and Urban Development posed a challenge of not displaying information that pertains to decentralisation and fiscal decentralisation aspects in particular.

1.10 Conclusion

This chapter has covered the introduction and methodology of the entire dissertation project and it discussed aspects such as the background of the problem, statement of the problem, objectives and research questions of the study, hypothesis, justification and methodology of the study. The following chapter will cover literature review and conceptual framework and the methodology of this study in full.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

2.0 Introduction

There has been considerable research about revenue mobilisation sources of local authorities all over the world in general and particularly in Zimbabwe. The aspect of revenue mobilisation in local authorities emerges from the concept of fiscal decentralisation an aspect of the general concept of decentralisation. Several scholars have written about revenue mobilisation strategies

in local authorities in general and they have shown that the aspect of revenue mobilisation sources is highly associated with the concept of fiscal decentralisation. This chapter seeks to review some literature which has been written concerning revenue mobilisation sources by local authorities. Also this chapter shall discuss the conceptual framework that is salient to the aspect of revenue mobilisation sources in Zimbabwe's urban councils in. The concept discussed herein is fiscal decentralisation. This chapter shall also focus on the methodology which is going to be used in collecting data about this study.

2.1 Literature Review and Conceptual Framework

Fjeldstad (2003:133) notes that fiscal decentralization has to do with handing over powers of taxing and spending to local authorities from central government. Marumahoko (2010:6) notes four main aspects which revolve around the concept of fiscal decentralisation and these aspects include: revenue, expenditure, intergovernmental fiscal transfers and borrowing. It is worth noting that the concept of fiscal decentralisation is one dimension of decentralisation. According to Ribott (2002:4), decentralisation is any act in which the central government formally cedes powers to actors and institutions at lower levels in a political-administrative and territorial hierarchy. Ribott (2002:5) notes that the reason for decentralising is justified in the sense that decentralisation reforms are usually about strengthening both central and local government in ways that support the objectives of national unification, democratisation and greater efficiency and equity in the use of public resources and service delivery. Pasipanodya et al (2000:31) highlight that decentralisation is characterised by public accountability, as the local self-government is subject to democratic control. Decentralisation allows citizens to participate in and influence the decisions made by the councils of local authorities. Decentralisation thus forms an important component of the development of democracy, as reflected in the European Charter of Local Self- Government adopted by the Council of Europe in 1985.

The UNDP document on fiscal decentralisation and poverty reduction (2010:2), notes that revenue means the availability of financial resources in urban councils to meet their expenditure projects and programs. The report highlights that the issue of urban council's revenue is two pronged in the sense that it first raises taxation responsibility between the central government and the local authority and the second aspect has to do with the sources of revenue mobilisation tasked to urban councils and the extent of discretion that local authorities have in mobilising revenue (UNDP 2010:4). Urban local authorities utilise various sources in generating revenue and these include: service fees, rates and fines. One of the major important

indicators of good fiscal decentralisation is the existence of constitutional or legislative acts for revenue mobilisation powers to be effective (UNDP 2010:8). From the document as highlighted above, it can be deduced that the aspect of revenue mobilisation is the fundamental pillar in the operations of local authorities and it strongly needs the backing of a constitutionalised decentralisation policy. Across the globe, the sources of revenue for urban councils seem to be similar although the strategies employed may differ from urban council to urban council and according to the legislative provisions of the state.

Marumahoko (2010:8) argues for the presence of constitutional backing for local authorities to have revenue raising powers. He cites examples of countries which have constitutional backing for revenue raising powers like South Africa where he notes that the 1996 Constitution of South Africa has provisions which grants fiscal powers to urban municipalities (Marumahoko 2010:9). Another given example is that of Nigeria, urban councils have the provision of generating revenue through constitutional means, for example, revenue mobilisation powers of local authorities are provided for in Section 7(1) of Nigeria's Constitution but this provision of revenue mobilisation by urban councils is subject to approval or disapproval by the central government. In comparison with Zimbabwe's local authorities, it is important to note that the existence of local governance in Zimbabwe was not constitutionally backed until recently when the 2013 constitution had to recognise the existence of local authorities legally. On the aspect of revenue for urban councils, Marumahoko (2010:11) posits that revenue mobilisation through legal and constitutional means alone is not enough but the extent of autonomy is also equally important. The main question at the end of the day is whether local authorities have adequate powers in mobilising revenue with minimum central government intervention.

Davey (1999:24) notes that fiscal decentralisation is generally accepted as the way to enhance political, institutional and economic development. The adoption of fiscal decentralisation in many developing countries is justified due to various reasons. One of the main reasons has to do with close interaction between the local government and the ratepayers. For example, fiscal decentralisation brings urban local governments are brought closer to ratepayers through implementation of fiscal decentralisation. Also through fiscal decentralisation, the tastes of the local communities are well satisfied as decisions are made in accordance with the needs of the community. According to the UNDP (2010:2) citizens within urban local governments are likely to be more willing to contribute financially in support of development activities that are identified and implemented at the local level and there is political accountability at local level.

UNDP (2010:5) highlights the aspect of borrowing by local authorities noting that urban local authorities must also be in a position to access loans and grants from lending institutions and enter into agreements with them with less intervention from the central government. As noted above, borrowing can be used as another strategy of mobilising revenue by local authorities and it can be classified as an external source of mobilising revenue.

Expenditure discretion is another aspect of fiscal decentralisation where urban councils commit and manage their funds without interference of central government, at their own discretion. Apart from the allocation of responsibilities, expenditure discretion is a good pointer of committed the central government is to the aspect of fiscal decentralisation. Furthermore, UNDP (2010:5) defines an intergovernmental fiscal transfer as budgetary funding from central government to urban councils for purposes of financing public services operations. Although intergovernmental financial transfers are used for a variety of purposes, they are mainly utilised to ensure the provision of additional resources to local authorities, so that there is equilibrium between their financial requirements and resources available. Finally, borrowing powers have to do with powers vested in urban councils enter into loan related agreements with willing financial institutions that deal with financial lending and borrowing.

Boex (2008:2) similarly notes that fiscal decentralisation is one component of decentralisation in which there are four tenets of fiscal decentralisation: (a) the theory of expenditure responsibilities, (b) the assignment of revenue sources to sub-national governments, (c) the provision of inter-governmental fiscal transfers or grants and (d) the framework for local borrowing and debt. Expenditure decentralization involves addressing questions such as what are the specific functions and expenditure responsibilities of each level of government at central, regional and local who will do what and who will pay?.

From the above mentioned aspects this study will mainly focus on the other three except expenditure since it does not fall in the category of revenue mobilisation strategies. The concept of fiscal decentralisation is also explained by scholars like Litvack (1999), who notes that fiscal decentralization takes a number of forms which include self-financing, co-financing with the private sector, intergovernmental transfer and local borrowing. The form of self-financing in this context is the concept of internal revenue mobilisation strategies. Therefore, fiscal decentralization can be defined as the devolution of policy responsibilities from central government towards local governments with regards to spending and revenue collection decisions.

In relation to this study this concept of fiscal decentralisation is seen to be relevant since it deals with ways of mobilising revenue and the greater extent of autonomy that is given to local authorities in managing their fiscal affairs at local level.

According to Magala and Rubagumya (2007:2) fiscal decentralisation policies in Uganda and Rwanda do not only have the mandate of planning, management and monitoring of local urban development but they are also granted legal autonomy and flexible decision making to mobilise and invest their financial resources. In both countries, transfers from central government and grants from the international community constitute close to 90% of financial resources available to local urban councils operations. These funds are mainly allocated by central government for the carrying out of specific programs which implies that centrally determined priorities may not meet locally felt needs (Magala and Rubagumya 2007:2). In their assessment the two scholars highlighted the importance of fiscal decentralisation in local authorities since they can meet the local desires of the citizens within the local town or city. Thus in as much as legal autonomy may be granted by the government, it's not enough to promote local growth in the local authorities. Instead of advancing the priorities of the central government, when local authorities are given the discretionary powers to raise and invest resources they will create a strong and sustainable fiscal capacity base.

The two scholars also note that, there is need for local governments to find means of enhancing local revenue mobilisation in a bid to respond to various challenges of dealing with local based needs so as to enhance the implementation of specific programs (Magala and Rubamguya 2007: 3). Thus there is a relationship between the locally based needs and the revenue base that can be created to mitigate these needs, which makes it important for local authorities to be legally autonomous in raising their own sources of revenue in the context of fiscal decentralisation. There is a general agreement amongst decentralisation authors that a viable local revenue base is central to the development and sustenance of a strong decentralised local government system. Local revenue among other things, promotes ownership and autonomy of the local governments (Local Finance Commission of Uganda 2003:4). Magala and Rubagumya (2007:3) gave some empirical evidence on the importance of these revenue sources in terms of their contribution to revenue base. For example in Rwanda, market fees contribute the highest percentage of the total revenue mobilised, about 60% of total revenue collected while in Uganda market fees represent the second highest source after graduated tax, market contribute close to 20% of the total locally mobilised revenue (Magala and Rubagumya 2007:3). Thus according to the two scholars, creating a revenue base is not the end and it will

not serve its actual purpose if the collection methods are not enhanced and strengthened legally and financially.

2.2 Methodology

Methodology refers to the research process and the kind of tools and procedures to be utilised in collecting data from the research participant (Barbie and Mouton 2001). The methods which will be used in this study include qualitative techniques and these include:

2.2.1 Research Design

It refers to the researcher's overall plan or blueprint on how the research is going to be conducted (Barbie and Mouton 2001). According Barbie and Mourton (2001) research design is a detailed plan on how one intends to carry out a research. An explorative descriptive survey design will be designed for this study and this study will use different instruments to collect data namely documentary search, questionnaires and interviews.

2.2.2 Target Population

This refers to a group to which the results of a study are intended to relate and from which those individuals selected to participate in a study are drawn. The target population for this study included officials of the Harare City Council, Department of revenue collection and the officials from the crucial organisations who are stakeholders with the Harare City Council like the Urban Councils Association of Zimbabwe (UCAZ), Harare Resident Trust (HRT), the former chairperson of the parliamentary portfolio committee on local government from 2009-2012.

2.2.3 Questionnaires

According to Payne and Payne (2004:186) questionnaires are the printed sets of questions to be answered by respondents, either through face-to-face interviews or self-completion, as a tested, structured, clearly presented and systematic means of collecting data (mainly in the quantitative methods tradition). Also, Coolican (2009) notes that a questionnaire is a written form used in gathering information on some subject or subjects consisting of a list of questions to be submitted to one or more persons. A questionnaire is most frequently a very concise, pre-planned set of questions designed to yield specific. In this study, questionnaires were used as one of the instruments to collect data key respondents will include the manager of the department of revenue collection at the Harare City Council, the director of the Urban Councils Association of Zimbabwe, and the chairperson of the Harare Residents Trust and scholars and lecturers at tertiary institutions like the University of Zimbabwe from the department of Political science and Administrative studies, who understand the concept of revenue collection

within local authorities and the former chairman of the parliamentary portfolio committee on local governance. One of the reasons why this instrument was chosen is because of its advantages which include, uniformity of questionnaires which make them to yield more data to be compared than information gathered through an interview or otherwise and they seem to be more objective than interviews since responses are gathered in a standardized manner. This instrument had its weaknesses as well which included data obtained from open ended questions can took a long time to process and analyse, also to some respondents the questionnaires took time to complete and the likelihood that the respondents could have answered superficially and produced distorted information

2.2.4 Interviews.

Payne and Payne (2004:129) highlights that interviewing is data collection in face-to-face settings, using an oral question-and-answer format which either employs the same questions in a systematic and structured way for all respondents, or allows respondents to talk about issues in less directed but discursive manner. Also according to Polit and Hungler (1991), interview is a method of collecting data through interaction involving an interviewer (person interviewing or asking questions) and an interviewee (person being interviewed or questioned) in order to obtain valid and reliable information. This study utilised interviews as a method in collecting the required data, and the target respondents using this method were the former chairperson of the parliamentary portfolio committee of local governance, the director of the Urban Councils Association of Zimbabwe and the management staff members from the department of revenue collection at the Harare City Council.

Just like other instruments and methods, the instrument showed its strength in the sense that interviewees responded in a manner comfortable to them, also the interviewer observed some verbal and non-verbal behaviour of respondents which proved to be another way of communication unlike in questionnaires where this could not be observed and the interviewee has room to ask for explanation on difficult questions. Shortfalls of this instrument were lack of expertise in the sense that both the interviewer and the interviewee could discuss questions that were not in the context of revenue mobilisation strategies, interviews at times failed to produce the necessary information when the researcher did not ask questions appropriately and some of the interviewees were unwilling to disclose information in the context of revenue collection and remittance of it as they said that was confidential information

2.2.5 Documentary Search

Payne and Payne (2004:60) describe the documentary search as the techniques used to categorise, investigate, interpret and identify most commonly written documents whether in the private or public domain. Punch (1998) documentary search use published information to support the viewpoint or argument of an academic and the documents used in documentary search include newspaper articles, books, journals and electronic interne). This study utilised books, journals, articles and internet information related to revenue mobilisation by local authorities in general and in particular the Harare City Council. This study used this method as another way of gathering data, both primary and secondary. Primary data in this context means research information which has not yet been published and is still raw data. For example raw data was obtained from an online research website called AFROBAROMETRE which is an independent, nonpartisan research project that measures the social, political, and economic atmosphere in Africa (<http://www.afrobarometer.org/>). Other sources of information used to gather data included the recorded parliamentary debate hansard booklets with information on local government and revenue mobilisation, primary or raw data from another organisation called Mass Public Opinion Institute (MPOI). Some journal and articles were utilised which were obtained from organisations such as the Urban Councils Association of Zimbabwe (UCAZ) and Harare Residents Trust (HRT). These had some information on local governance management in respect to revenue mobilisation techniques which the Harare City Council employs.

2.2.6 Sampling Procedures

Two types of sampling are going to be used which are purposive and snowballing. Purposive sampling is a method which is based on the judgement of the researcher regarding the desired characteristics of the representative sample. It also targets a particular group of people so that the researcher purposefully selects the research participants and its power lies in selecting information, rich cases for in-depth analysis related to the central issues being studied (De vos 2005). Snowball sampling is a technique whereby researchers request participants to provide information about other potential respondents with the same characteristics.

2.2.7 Data Presentation

Creswell (2005:139) states that the aim of qualitative research is to describe certain aspects of a phenomenon with a view of explaining the subject of the study. Data shall be summarised in ways that reveal information necessary to confirm or reject the hypothesis and hence pie charts, bar graphs and tables shall be used.

2.2.8 Data Analysis

Creswell (2005:184) highlights that data analysis in the qualitative research consist on preparing and organising the data for analysis, then reduce data into themes through a process of coding and considering the codes and finally present the data in figures, tables or discussion. Hence grouping data into themes will make the analysis of data easy and manageable for this study.

2.3 Conclusion

This chapter has discussed the literature and conceptual framework of this study, highlighting some key text and authors who have wrote about fiscal decentralisation and revenue mobilisation in local authorities in other countries in the continent of African and the world in general. Also the methodology aspect of the study has been discussed, outlining the methods and instruments that this study will use in collecting data, presenting it and analysing it. The following chapter will focus on the findings and analysis from the field works.

CHAPTER 3: FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

3.0 Introduction

This chapter presents and analyses the findings of the study. It focuses on answering the research questions and objectives of the study which are: finding out the sources of revenue used by Harare City Council; factors that affect the collection of revenue; and the effectiveness of these sources towards service delivery. The chapter also relates the findings to the hypothesis that: *sustainable sources of revenue strengthen the fiscal capacity of local authorities.*

3.1 Respondents Interviewed

The respondents interviewed in this research include a council official from the revenue collection department at Harare City Council (HCC), program officers from pressure groups such as Harare Residents Trust (HRT), Urban Councils Association of Zimbabwe (UCAZ) and Combined Harare Residents Association (CHRA) and the Committee Clerk of the Parliamentary Portfolio Committee on Local Governance, Rural and Urban Planning. This distribution of respondents was chosen in such a way that it would balance the data gathering process considering the fact that data gathered will not be susceptible to subjectivity as some of the interviewees are drawn from pressure groups that represent residents in Harare like Harare Residents Trust and Combined Harare Residents Association.

Table 1: Interview Schedule.

Interviewee	Date of interview	Time of interview	Place
Revenue Collection Manager Harare City Council (HCC)	10 March 2014	10:00 am	Rowan Martin Building
Programs Officer Urban Councils Association of Zimbabwe (UCAZ)	10 March 2014	14:00pm	Insurance House (NICOZ DIAMOND)
Committees Officer Harare Residents Trust (HRT)	13 March 2014	10:00am	HRT offices, Tudor Gardens, Avenues
Programs Officer , Combined Harare Residents Association (CHRA)	14 March 2014	09:00am	CHRA offices, 12 Oxford drive, Newlands
Committee Clerk, parliamentary portfolio committee on Local Government, Rural and Urban Development	14 March 2014	14:00pm	Parliament of Zimbabwe

3.2 Challenges Encountered During Fieldwork.

During data collection in the field, the researcher found three important aspects that are essential to highlight from the onset. The first aspect concerns the terminological mix-up between the terms ‘strategy’ and ‘source’. The term strategy as used in the case of Harare City Council means ways of making residents to pay up their bills and meet their obligations to the City Council, for example, legal means which involve the courts and bill discounting to residents among others. The term ‘source’ of revenue refers to ways used to acquire revenue for the City Council, for example, rates or tax on property, water sales, income generating projects, and licence and user fees among others. In light of this study, in the previous chapters,

the researcher has been using the term strategies instead of sources which brought confusion during fieldwork. In light of this, this paper will use the appropriate term which is sources instead of strategies as indicated before.

The second aspect is of limited access to adequate data pertaining to this study, particularly the statistical reports on the performance of the sources of revenue that the Harare City Council utilises. One of the reasons that led to this limitation in acquiring adequate information was the exposure of the so called “salary gate scandal” in local parastatals and local authorities particularly Harare City Council. Due to suspicion and fear of further exposure and investigation the City Council personnel were not willing to take part in this research. Data presented in this chapter was obtained from the Revenue Collection Manager from the department of Revenue Collection as it is the authorised department sanctioned to release financial information pertaining to Treasury matters of the City Council.

The third challenge that was encountered in fieldwork was the loss of the researcher’s laptop due to theft. This had a negative impact as all the collected data from fieldwork was lost including the research notes that were handwritten. Progress that was made in collecting data was halted as all data collected was lost and the researcher had to start again from start.

3.3 Sources of Revenue Utilised by Harare City Council

Revenue instruments used by Zimbabwe's local authorities include: rates-property tax, water sales, sewerage management, refuse collection, lease rentals for land and buildings, vehicle licences, shop licences, clinic and hospital fess, market stall fees, on-street parking fees, parking lots, commuter omnibus rank charges and building plans approval fees (UCAZ International review 2008). Harare City Council enjoys a wide base of sources which it uses to mobilise revenue just like any other local authorities in Zimbabwe as enshrined within the Urban Councils Act [29:15]. Sachikonye (2007:80) notes that Zimbabwe Urban Councils enjoy greater operational autonomy with substantive own resources as opposed to rural district councils which rely to a greater extent on fiscal transfers of service delivery by Central Government. Of all the sources used by the Harare City Council, the Revenue Collection Manager of the City Council noted that there are four main sources which generate more revenue than the others and these are: rates/tax on property, water sales, refuse removal and sewer system repairs. This is attributed to the fact that the four sources are now compounded

on one bill that is paid by the residents. That is the water bill, rates, sewerage and refuses collection fees are billed once and paid as a single council bill.

As indicated in Table 2, rates/property tax and water sales contribute most to the revenue base.

Table 2: Highest sources of Revenue utilised by City of Harare as of 2011.

Source of revenue	Contribution to the City Council revenue base in percentage
Rates/property tax	25%
Water Sales	21%
Refuse charges	14%
Sewerage charges	13%
Lease rentals	8%
Markets fees	8%
Parking fees	7%
Other	4%
Total	100%

Source: City of Harare, City Treasures Management Report (2009-2011).

3.3.1 Rates/Property Tax, Water Sales, Sewerage and Refuse Charges

Coutinho (2010) highlights the sources of revenue that Zimbabwe's urban councils utilise as provided for by the Urban Councils Act [29:15] (1996). According to Section 269(1) of the Urban Councils Act, revenue can be mobilised through the use of rates as a source of revenue for local authorities. Rates tax is the revenue that is collected from all urban houses and land within the jurisdiction of the City of Harare. According to the Revenue Collection Manager of the City of Harare, the revenue from property tax constitutes the highest percentage due to the fact that there has been a steady increase in property acquisition and development by the residents in the City of Harare. He noted that the increase of property has risen from 190 000 in 2009 to 220 000 as of 2013 end of year. Thus about 30 000 residential properties developed within a time frame of four years. These properties in terms of billing as highlighted before are compounded and they are placed on the billing row of rates which can explain the increase in potential billing of US\$18 million in 2009 rising to US\$22 million as of 2013 year end.

The Revenue Collection Manager at the City of Harare highlighted that compared to the pre-2009 era the period in question saw an improvement in terms of revenue collection as there was a gradual increase in relation to the revenue collection rate of the sources utilised by the City Council. This performance can be attributed to the introduction of multi- currency system. The Parliament Portfolio Committee Clerk of Local Government, Rural and Urban

Development, also concurred to this position, noting that the introduction of the multi-currency saw the City of Harare making realistic budgets and revenue collection targets that could be followed through in budget and council treasury reviews as well. It was brought to the attention of the researcher that from 2009 onwards revenue collection rate ranged from 60%-65% for rates and water sales only as indicated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Revenue collection rate (in percentage) from 2009-2011 (Compounded: Rates and Water sales)

Source: City of Harare, City Treasures management report (2009-May 2011).

Figure 1 above shows the revenue collection rates for City Council from 2009-2011. According to the Figure 1 there was a steady increase in terms of the revenue collection rate of water sales and rates. In 2009 the percentage was around 54%, and in 2010 the percentage rate rose to 60%. As of 2011 the percentage of revenue collection rate of water sales and rates increased to 65%. As noted before, this performance can be attributed to the introduction of real value currencies compared to the Zimbabwean dollar, which were introduced to the economic system at macro-level.

3.3.2 Lease/Rental Charges and Licence Fees.

According to Coutinho (2010:76) the majority of local urban councils possess properties, such as, houses and flats, as well as commercial buildings, which they lease out. The land is either rented out to various institutions, individuals or organisations or it is sold out for commercial or residential purposes. This is an important source of funding for most councils in Zimbabwe and the leasing or selling of land owned by council is increasingly proving to be the crucial source of revenue for local urban councils in Zimbabwe. The funds raised are normally credited

to the Estates Account of the council. Harare City Council owns a lot of properties both domestic and commercial which is rented out or leased. The 2012 budget review indicates that the revenue which was collected from rentals and leasing of property was only US\$10 553 300, which was only about 4% of the total revenue collected. This was a significant drop from the 2011 collections which were at 8% of the total revenue collected. For example, the revenue collection department of the Harare City notes that the city liquor premises in Harare, leased to liquor business operators, have rental areas of about US\$1 799 711.44 while in domestic properties the residents renting council properties in high density areas such as Highfileds, Mbare, Budiriro and Dzivarasekwa alone, owe the City Council about US\$8 476 053.44.

This significant drop in revenue collection can possibly be attributed to several factors such as, failure to regularly review the rates of rentals accordingly, lack of an updated database of council leased properties, that is, land and buildings and finally at times the rentals are charged at very low rates which gives in an insignificant value in terms of contributions to the councils revenue. This problem was still present in 2011 of which it remains one of the challenges that the City Council of Harare face.

3.3.3 Licence Fees

Couthinho (2010:75) notes that license fees relate to items, such as, vehicle licenses, dog licenses, hawker's licenses, shop licenses, etc. Vehicle licence fee is charged on certain classes of vehicles as described by the Vehicle Registration and Licencing Act [13:14]. The Harare City council used to get most of its licencing revenue from vehicle licencing before the mandate to collect vehicle taxes was assigned to Zimbabwe National Roads Administration (ZINARA) in 2010. The Revenue Collection Manager of Harare City council gave more insight concerning vehicle licencing, noting that the City council feels short-changed by ZINARA as the new licencing authority is failing to remit adequate funds to the City of Harare. For example the City of Harare in 2009 when it was still collecting revenue from vehicle licencing, it collected a total of US\$7.4 million and in 2012 after ZINARA took over the task, the Council only received about US\$1.25 million in an environment where capacity had increased due to the increase in vehicle population in the city, according to CHRA 2012 City of Harare budget review summary. The effect of this situation is that the Harare city council will have to bear the heavy burden where the council will divide the revenue from rates and channel some of it to maintain the city roads. Thus the net effect will be inadequate provision of service delivery by the City of Harare as revenue collected will not equal to the expenditure met in providing the required services.

3.3.4 Central Government Allocation

Couthinho (2010:81) notes that the central government has been releasing a certain percentage of funds to local authorities in various forms. For example, the central government through the Reserve Bank of Zimbabwe, has been financing some of the operations of the local authorities in a bid to ensure a continued better quality of service delivery especially on water provision and sewerage maintenance during the period 2005-2007. According to the Reserve Bank of Zimbabwe report of September 2007, on Local Authorities Re-Orientation Program (LARP), Harare City Council received about 32.15% of the total amount of the disbursements. The central government funding was provided by central government in the form of long term loans and grants. The revenue collection manager of the City of Harare highlighted that the City used to receive per capita grants of about 50% which was channelled to health expenditure and salaries of medical staff. Also the city used to receive funds for the maintenance of trunk roads such as Samora Machel, Enterprise road, Robert Mugabe road and Beatrice road etc. In light of this information it was established that during the period under study, no government allocation was received by the City of Harare and the above mentioned expenditure heads are now financed by revenue collected from other sources utilised by the City council so the City council will provide adequate service to the residents and its clients.

3.3.5 Loans and Grants from Non-Government Sources.

According to Coutinho (2010:81) infrastructure such as water and sewerage equipment, computers and vehicles have been funded for by the World Bank in the past years. Local Authorities also have borrowing powers according to Coutinho (2010:82), under this instrument of revenue mobilisation, all borrowings should be authorised by the Minister of Local Government, Urban and Rural Planning. The programmes officer from urban councils association of Zimbabwe (UCAZ) concurs with Coutinho in arguing that a council is eligible to borrow from foreign financial institutions, governments and individuals as well.

Between 2010 – 2013, Harare City Council received loans and grants amounting to US \$163.5 million from three financial institutions: The African Development Bank (AFDB), BancABC and China-EximBank. China-EximBank had the largest percentage of the total grants and loans received by Harare City Council as shown in Figure 2 below. A report by the Parliamentary Portfolio Committee on Local Government, Rural and Urban development (2010), on the state of service delivery by municipalities of Harare, Chitungwiza and Norton highlights that the in

2010, the City Council secured a loan of US \$10 million from BancABC bank. This was for the acquisition of refuse collection vehicles as well as improving other council services. In 2012 and 2013 the City of Harare also secured a loan and a grant from the China EximBank and the African Development Bank (AFDB), respectively. These were also secured in a bid to revamp and improve service delivery particularly by rehabilitating the water works pumps at Morton Jaffray. The herald of 19 June 2013, reports that Harare City Council had secured about us\$153 million grant from China-EximBank and the African Development Bank for the comprehensive rehabilitation of the city's water treatment works. The article further highlights that the town clerk Dr. Tendai Mahachi gave a breakdown of the grant to the committee. The town clerk highlighted that AFDB availed US\$9.5 million and the China-EximBank also injected us\$144 million. (The Herald 19/06/13).

The utilisation of such an instrument of revenue mobilisation saw the City of Harare managing to acquire the much needed refuse collection vehicles, rehabilitation at the Morton Jaffray water works pumps and the installation of high lift pumps and ancillaries at Prince Edward water works (*The Herald 16/06/13*).

Figure 2: Loans and Grants received by Harare City Council (2010-2013).

Sources: *Parliamentary Portfolio Committee on Local Government, Rural and Urban development (2010), Report on the State of Service Delivery by Municipalities of Harare, Chitungwiza and Norton cited in (The Herald 19/06/13).*

3.4 Factors Perceived as obstacle in revenue mobilisation during the period 2009-2013.

Revenue mobilisation during the period in question faced various obstacles which are perceived to have hindered the collection of city council's financial resources. These perceived obstacles include: complicated and non-transparent local authority revenue collection system, high unemployment rate, limited access to foreign currency by ratepayers, corruption and an outdated data capturing system. These factors are explained in detail below.

3.4.1 Complicated and non-transparent local authority revenue collection system

Makwembere (2012:2) argues that local authorities capacity to provide service to rate payers is determined by the fiscal capacity of the local authorities and the fiscal capacity is determined by the factors that can enhance or inhibit revenue mobilisation. Several challenges faced by the Harare City Council in mobilising revenue during the period in question were noted by the targeted respondents to this study. Bardan and Mookherje (2002 in Makwembere 2012:18) note that one of the chief challenges in revenue mobilisation is the presence of a complicated and non-transparent local authority revenue collection system which is costly to administer as it facilitates corruption and mismanagement. This aspect of non-transparency from the City of Harare was also noted by the programs officer of CHRA, when he argued that most of the budget consultations, approval and reviews were done with less or no participation by the

residents or rate payers in the process. This becomes an obstacle in the sense that most rate payers will either refuse to pay or delay in paying for the charges that the city of Harare will have stipulated.

3.4.2 High Unemployment Rate

Another challenge that the City of Harare faced in mobilising revenue was the high unemployment rate. The rate of unemployment is a contested issue between independent economists for example, according to the Central Intelligence Factbook (CIA) (01/01/2011), the unemployment rate was at 95% and the central Government through its agent Zimbabwe National Statistics Agency (ZIMSTAT) argued that it is at 10.7%. HRT and the Revenue Collection Manager of the Harare City noted with great concern the high level of unemployment which prevailed and still prevails in nation. Arguing that for Harare City Council to collect adequate revenue from rate payers, it was a mammoth task since rate payers were unable to pay their monthly bills and their debts continued accumulating. This is evidenced by the city treasury's management report of 2011, noting that Harare City is owed a debt of US\$154 million from 2009 to 31 May 2011 yet the annual budget for 2010 was at US\$185 million. Thus the debtor's position was at 83% of the City's annual budget (City of Harare, City Treasurer Management report 2011). This means that the actual targeted revenue could not be met and the implication in relation to service delivery would be negative as service delivery will continue to dwindle in a council with great potential of instruments of revenue mobilisation.

3.4.3 Access to Foreign Currency by Ratepayers

Closely related to the above, the issue of multi-currency system which was introduced in February 2009 also posed as a challenge in the collection of revenue by the City of Harare. CHRA programs officer noted that when the multi-currency system was adopted in 2009, most of the ratepayers in the city were unable to access the foreign currency as some of them were unemployed and some had just lost their savings in banks which were eroded by inflation during the economic meltdown era. This point was further stressed by the Revenue Collection Manager of Harare City Council who highlighted that, most residents in the city failed to pay their bills during the period when the multicurrency system was adopted in 2009.

3.4.4 Corruption

Another challenge that the City Council faced in collecting revenue was the rampant corruption levels on the reconnection of water supplies and defaulting residents. According to

Afrobarometer cited on Nehanda Radio website, in an article titled: “ Zimbabwe ranked third most corrupt country in Africa”, it is perceived to be a problem by 81% of adult Zimbabweans, falling just behind Nigeria and Egypt which are at 82% (Nehanda Radio 21/12/13). According to a report by HRT on Harare water exposure (2013), the organisation noted that there is alleged rampant corruption on the reconnection of water supplies to defaulters. When workers are asked to go and disconnect water, they are served with a written directive which shows the amount a consumer owes to the Council. However, the management follows up with verbal orders directing the very same staff to go and reconnect the water without any monies being paid to the City Council, prejudicing the council in the process. An example of such a scenario is of the “City Council versus Sifra Village and Hebert Chitepo Cooperative” that has 464 units and both owed the Council US\$23 000 apiece. It is reported that for 11hrs following water disconnection, using a works order, staff were directed to restore water supplies with the directive coming from senior management. The outstanding debt was subsequently wiped off during the debt relief directive from Central Government. In the end, this results in little revenue being collected against the huge expenditure budget of which in the end the quality of service delivery will be compromised.

3.4.4 Outdated data capturing system

Other challenges faced by the City of Harare in collecting revenue include inadequate data capturing in relation to the actual number of taxed properties and land within the City and this has led to revenue leakages. Also the revenue manager at the City of Harare noted that the aftermath of the economic crisis of 2008 saw industries operating at 20% and the City Council continues billing rates on “white elephant” buildings. This means that the revenue from property tax in relation to taxable industrial buildings is not realised due to industrial underutilisation capacity. Also the unemployment rate which was about 70% led to some unemployed residents to default in paying tax on domestic properties.

3.5 The Relationship between a Strong Revenue Base and Service Delivery.

Makwembere (2012:78) argues that service delivery in all the urban councils has plummeted due to lack of adequate financial resources and funding. This means that for the best quality of service delivery to be rendered, the Harare City Council must have a strong revenue base and fiscal capacity. For example, in 2009 the local authority had 2 refuse trucks and now they have 54 trucks which is a positive development. This can further be buttressed by the comparative analysis on the estimate of actual revenue collections between the City of Harare and the town council of Chitungwiza 2012, indicated in figure 3 below.

Figure 3 depicts the results of a survey conducted by the Revenue Collection Manager of the Harare City Council in a bid to link the relationship of the local authorities' revenue base with its effect on the quality of service delivery. The respondents in this survey were mainly the council officials from the two local authorities and they included the town clerks of the councils, heads of departments, managers, supervisors and stakeholders of the two councils. As indicated in Figure 3, Harare City Council had respondents slightly above 60% who agreed that the estimate of budgeted annual revenue can be around US\$282 million in order to perform efficiently and its actual annual revenue collection over 80% of the respondents noted that the Harare City Council collects an average of US\$150 million annually. This means that though the Harare City Council has a greater potential of collecting revenue above US\$250 million per year, the actual revenue collection of about US\$150 million indicates that the revenue base is weak such that it cannot sustain its operations hence the poor service delivery.

In comparison, the Chitungwiza town council 40% of the respondents were of the view that the town council can generate revenue above US\$70 million meaning that the collection must be maximised to sustain council operations. However, the Chitungwiza Town Council in its actual annual revenue collections gets the annual revenue collection of about US\$50-60 million which is indicated by 54% of the respondents concurring to this estimate. This indicates that the revenue collected falls far short beyond the required annual revenue for good service delivery to be rendered.

Figure 3: A Survey Estimate of budgeted and actual annual revenue collections for both Harare City Council and Chitungwiza Town Council (2012).

SOURCE: MAKWEMBERE (2012), *A comparative study of revenue collection strategies in urban local authorities in Zimbabwe.*

3.6 Hypothesis Testing

The data gathered during fieldwork was used to test the hypothesis of this research which is: *sustainable sources of revenue strengthen the fiscal capacity of local authorities.* Data gathered from fieldwork indicates that the hypothesis can be validated to a certain extent. It has been confirmed that it is not the revenue base alone that can strengthen the fiscal capacity of local authorities but other factors such as the level of political intervention and the tenets of good corporate governance which are accountability and transparency also have a role in shaping the fiscal capacity of local authorities.

3.7 Conclusion

Harare City Council has a wide range of instruments or sources of mobilising revenue which are both internal and external. As indicated in this chapter, both instruments are legally sanctioned for utilisation through the Urban Councils Act [25:19]. During the 2009-2012 these instruments can be said to have been effective and useful in mobilising revenue particularly considering the introduction of the multi-currency system in 2009. The performance of these sources could be easily tracked and also realistic budgets could be crafted and reviewed due to the introduction of a multi-currency system which brought some level of normalcy to the economic environment of the nation at large and local authorities in particular. Challenges and factors that can hinder revenue collection have also been highlighted in this chapter so were the examples which show the level of their negative effect in mobilisation of revenue.

In relation to service delivery, this chapter established that quality service delivery is highly related to sound and strong financial capacity since the issue of service delivery revolves around aspects of financial resources playing a prominent role. The hypothesis of this study was validated to a certain extent, as it was proven that effective sources of revenue are, but one pillar of a strong fiscal capacity of local authorities. Other crucial pillars include minimum levels of political intervention and upholding of principles of good governance. The following chapter is going to present the conclusions and recommend actions that can be taken so that revenue mobilisation can be improved as well as service delivery.

CHAPTER 4: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the conclusions and recommendations of the study based on the findings from the previous chapter. The previous chapter attempted to answer questions such as: What are the sources of revenue utilised by the Harare City Council? What factors can be considered to be an obstacle in mobilising revenue? How effective are these sources in strengthening the fiscal capacity of the City of Harare? , lastly, Can effective revenue mobilisation enhance service delivery? Chapter three attempted to answer these questions and this chapter will make some conclusions based on the major findings from the previous chapter. The chapter also presents the possible recommendations that can be utilised in relation to the challenges that the Harare City Council is facing in mobilising revenue.

4.1 Conclusions

4.1.1 Sources utilised by the Harare City Council in revenue mobilisation.

The Harare City Council enjoys a broad base of sources or instruments of revenue mobilisation as stipulated by the Urban Council Act [25:19] as well as some of their own creative means of mobilising revenue sanctioned by the Minister of Local Government, Rural and Urban development. The various sources include: rates on property and land, revenue from water sales, revenue from user fees such as council schools, clinics and hospitals, licence fees from shop owners, private transport operators and hawkers, fines and penalties from illegal parking by motorists in the City, hawkers who sell at undesignated places, leased properties of the City Council and finally Loans and Grants. Other sources of revenue utilised by the Harare City Council include quarry stone sales and farming activities at the city farm.

4.1.2 Various obstacles faced by Harare City Council in revenue mobilisation.

Harare City Council faces various obstacles in mobilising its revenue, and most of these obstacles can be attributed to factors such as high levels of political intervention particularly when the politicians want to advance their political mileage using council as an instrument to achieve their political gains, for example, the 2013 June/July debt cancellation proclaimed by the government. The economic meltdown in the nation which left huge industries suffering from underutilisation compared to their anticipated capacity of operation also contributed as an obstacle in revenue mobilisation for the City Council. This resulted in them failing to pay rates and water bills to the City Council as well. Related to the above factor is the aspect of unemployment rate which was high resulting in most of the unemployed residents defaulting

in paying their bills and ended up accumulating huge amounts of debts, money owed to the City Council.

4.1.3 Sources utilised by Harare City Council and their effectiveness in of strengthening the fiscal capacity of the City Council.

Findings indicated that the sources utilised by Harare City Council proved to be effective in strengthening the fiscal capacity of the City Council. This can be attributed to the introduction of the multicurrency system which brought economic stability and also the currencies that were adopted were of real value and the Council could make real budgets both estimated and actual budgets after reviews. This is evidenced by the revenue collection rate or operating rate which rose from 40% to 60-65% as the Revenue Collection Manager of the City of Harare indicated. If managed properly and enhanced by feasible strategies this collection capacity can even go beyond the current 60-65%.

4.1.4 Effective utilisation of revenue mobilisation sources enhances the quality of service delivery by the City Council.

Findings in this research indicates that effective revenue mobilisation and adequate utilisation of sources of revenue results in strong fiscal capacity which in turn will lead to an improved and good service delivery by the Harare city Council. This shows that the quality of service that the City of Harare delivers is largely determined by the fiscal capacity of the City Council. If the fiscal capacity is poor, then the service will be highly compromised and if the capacity is high and sound, service delivery will be of good quality.

4.2 Recommendations.

4.2.1 Amend the Urban Councils Act in line with the New Constitution.

It is imperative that the Urban Councils Act [25:19] be amended in line with the new Constitution of Zimbabwe which gives provisions on how local authorities are to be administered right from the election of leaders to the financing of the local authorities. For example, the new Constitution of Zimbabwe, under chapter 17, section 301(3), stipulates that no less than 5% of the national revenue raised in any financial year must be allocated to the provinces and local authorities as their share in that year. Also the new Act should curtail the powers of the Minister of Local Government such that the level of political intervention will be minimised and autonomy to local authorities will be guaranteed with less compromise.

4.2.2 Need to Formulate and Fully Implement the service charter (social contract) between residents and the City Council.

There is also need to craft and fully implement a service charter (social contract) between the residents and the city council that binds the two parties to fully oblige to the terms and conditions of service provision. In this case parties will have the power and will to make litigations against the party at fault.

4.2.3 The City Council must revamp its System of administration to curb the problem of revenue leakages.

It is also equally important that the Harare City Council must revamp its system of administration such that revenue leakage holes will be plugged and the database system be revised, computerised and accessed from the central office. This can be done through the computerisation and connection of all district offices to the main server at Rowan Martin through the Local Area Network (LAN) and Wide Area Network (WAN) and implement the intranet facility. This system will monitor and account for the day to day billing transactions from the district offices to the head office.

4.2.4 Reducing the wage bill of administrative staff receiving hefty salaries at the City Council.

In terms of expenditure budget, it is highly recommended that the central government in consultation with both the city council and residents should help in regulating the wage bill of all the high ranking administration staff receiving hefty salaries to reasonable salaries such that revenue mobilised will not only be consumed in expenditure budget alone but also channelled towards delivering the required quality of service.

4.2.5 Enhance Resident Participation in decision making process of the City Council's Business.

Efforts should be increased towards involvement of resident participation in the decision making process of the Harare City Council. This includes budget proposal participation, budget review meetings and annual general meetings and other crucial meetings in which residents are important stakeholders. This will increase the level of transparency and accountability and it will also boost the level of confidence and trust in the City Council by the residents. In turn, residents will take part in planning and implementation of revenue related business with full cooperation as they will understand the importance of a strong revenue base and effective service delivery.

4.3 Conclusion.

This chapter focused on the conclusions and recommendations based on the major findings from chapter three. This chapter concluded that from the wide range of sources utilised in the mobilisation of revenue, Harare city council relies with four main sources of revenue which are: property tax, water sales, refuse collection charges and sewerage system repairs. Various obstacles in mobilising revenue during the period understudy were also discussed and these include: high levels of political intervention, unemployment rate which has prevailed since the economic meltdown. The economic meltdown also left many industries suffering from underutilisation of their actual operational capacity. These sources also proved to be effective in strengthening the fiscal capacity of the City Council provided that they are properly managed and complimented by upholding of good governance principles. This chapter also proffered some recommendations which can be effected in a bid to improve the performance of the mentioned sources of revenue, strengthen the fiscal capacity of local authorities and improve the quality of service delivery.

This study in short, attempted to unravel sources of revenue in Zimbabwe's local authorities and their performance in enhancing service delivery since the introduction of multicurrency system in 2009. Furthermore this study proved that sustainable sources of revenue alone cannot fully strengthen the fiscal capacity of local authorities. Sustainable sources of revenue can be augmented with minimum level of political and central government intervention and the promotion of good governance principles in local authorities. Finally, recommendations were proffered in a bid to enhance the mobilisation of revenue and the sustainability of these sources. Chief among some of the recommendations were: amending the Urban Councils Act [25:19] to be consistent with the new Constitution of Zimbabwe, enhancing citizen participation in the decision making process of the City Council and minimising the level of central and political intervention among others.

Although this study attempted to unravel all the salient aspects of fiscal decentralisation particularly the aspect of revenue mobilisation, much could not be covered due the delimitations, limitations, and time and space limitations. This area of study still has more issues to be unravelled and different perspectives of revenue mobilisation to be explored, which becomes the remaining gap for other researchers and practitioners to further review and take this study to another research level.

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Appendix One: Interview Guide.

INTERVIEW GUIDE

My name is **Gerald J.T MANDISODZA (R101564X)**, a student at the University of Zimbabwe currently doing Bachelor of Science Special Honours in Political science and Administrative studies. I am conducting a research on the effectiveness of revenue mobilisation sources in Zimbabwe's local authorities: A case of Harare City Council from 2009-2013. I kindly ask for your assistance in providing answers to my research inquiry. Responses given will be treated with confidentiality and all information provided will be used strictly for academic purposes.

Interview Questions

1. From a list of all the sources of revenue utilised by Harare City Council, can you kindly mention four main sources which contribute more to the revenue base of the City Council?
2. Can you briefly comment about the introduction of the multicurrency system in 2009, in relation to revenue mobilisation, fiscal capacity of the City Council and the aspect of service delivery?
3. During the period from 2009-2013, can you briefly comment on the performance of the sources utilised to mobilise revenue by the Harare City Council?
4. The hand-over take-over of vehicle licencing mandate from Harare City Council to Zimbabwe National Roads Administration (ZINARA) is perceived to have negatively affected the mobilisation of revenue in local authorities. To what extent has this process affected the mobilisation of revenue by Harare City Council?
5. How can you describe the relationship between sustainable sources of revenue and fiscal capacity of local authorities in relation to the quality of service delivery by the City Council?

Appendix Two: Questionnaire Guide.

Questionnaire Guide

My name is **Gerald J.T MANDISODZA (R101564X)**, a student at the University of Zimbabwe currently doing Bachelor of Science Special Honours in Political science and Administrative studies. I am conducting a research on the effectiveness of revenue mobilisation sources in Zimbabwe's local authorities: A case of Harare City Council from 2009-2013. I kindly ask for your assistance in providing answers to my research inquiry. Responses given will be treated with confidentiality and all information provided will be used strictly for academic purposes.

Position of Respondent:

Department:

Date:

1. From the list below, can you mark the sources of revenue utilised by the Harare City Council?

- | | |
|---|--------------------------|
| I. Rates on property and land | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| II. Revenue from water sales | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| III. Revenue from user fees e.g. council schools, flea markets etc. | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| IV. Central government allocation | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| V. Licence fees from shop owners ,hawkers and vehicle owners | <input type="checkbox"/> |

VI. Fines and penalties e.g. illegal parking, unauthorised transport operators (commuter

omnibuses, private taxies)

2. If there are any sources of revenue listed in (1) above, can you kindly list them below?

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3. From the list above, which Source(s) do you think contributes more to the revenue base of the Harare City Council?

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4. What reasons can you attribute to the better performance of the above sources?

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5. What could possibly be attributed to the poor performance of the other source which did not contribute well to the revenue base?

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6. Comparing with the pre-2009 period, do you think that the sources utilised from 2009 – 2012 improved the revenue base of Harare City Council?

- I. YES
- II. NO

7. Can you list reasons to support your answer above?

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7. Can you list some of the challenges that the Harare City Council faced in mobilising revenue during the period 2009-2012?

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8. Can you explain the relationship between a strong revenue base and service delivery of Harare City Council?

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9. What recommendations can you suggest to improve revenue mobilisation by the Harare City Council in a bid to strengthen fiscal capacity and improve service delivery?

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Thank you for your cooperation.